

CHARACTERIZATION AND DESIGN OF CARBON-TRC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

For a safe and reliable structural design with textile reinforced concrete (TRC), an appropriate characterization of materials is necessary in a way to obtain representative properties. In this work, tensile and compressive properties of carbon-TRC composites as well as the carbon-concrete interface are characterized for four coating conditions. Different testing methods were used to obtain directly and indirectly the constitutive relations. To determine the most suitable characterization techniques, the relations were applied to a theoretical beam model and the results were compared to experiments. It was concluded that properties determined from tensile tests with specimens attached to the grips with screws and having a width of 80 mm and a gauge length of 400 mm were the most adequate for moment-curvature and moment-crack opening predictions.

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KEYWORDS

Textile reinforced concrete; Carbon fibers; Coating; Mechanical characterization; Structural design.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.